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2 **Potential Distinct Impacts of Global Warming on Mesoscale Convective Systems and**
3 **Isolated Deep Convection in the Central-eastern United States**

4 **Jianfeng Li¹, Yun Qian¹, L. Ruby Leung¹, Weiran Liu², Kai Zhang¹, Paul Ullrich^{2,3},**
5 **Lingcheng Li¹, Ye Liu¹, Huilin Huang¹, Zeyu Xue¹**

6 ¹Atmospheric, Climate, and Earth Sciences Division, Pacific Northwest National Laboratory;
7 Richland, Washington, USA

8 ²Department of Land, Air, and Water Resources, University of California, Davis, Davis, CA,
9 USA

10 ³Division of Physical and Life Sciences, Lawrence Livermore National Laboratory, Livermore,
11 CA, USA

12 Corresponding authors: Jianfeng Li (jianfeng.li@pnnl.gov) and Yun Qian (yun.qian@pnnl.gov)

13 **Key Points:**

- 14 • A regionally-refined global cloud-resolving model is used to investigate how global
15 warming affects convective systems of different sizes
- 16 • In a warmer summer atmosphere, mesoscale convective systems (MCSs) become more
17 frequent, while isolated deep convection (IDC) diminishes
- 18 • Summertime MCSs and IDC tend to occur closer to the southern and eastern coastal areas
19 of the United States under warming
20

21 **Abstract**

22 Using the regionally refined Simple Cloud-Resolving E3SM (Energy Exascale Earth System
23 Model) Atmosphere Model and the pseudo-global warming experiment framework, we
24 investigate the potential impact of global warming on convective storms of different sizes and
25 lifetimes in the central-eastern United States from July 1 to August 19, 2020. We find an increase
26 in the number of large and long-lasting mesoscale convective systems (MCSs) but a decrease in
27 small and short-duration isolated deep convection (IDC) events in a warming scenario following
28 the Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSP5-8.5). Although the mean MCS lifetime becomes
29 shorter under warming, IDC events persist longer. Also, regions with the most frequent MCS and
30 IDC occurrences shift significantly: MCSs and IDC tend to occur closer to the southern and
31 eastern coasts, where the relative humidity of the environment increases under global warming.
32 This work unveils the complexity of the response of convective systems to climate change.

33 **Plain Language Summary**

34 Convective systems are vital to the Earth's hydrological cycle, atmospheric circulation, and
35 radiation balance. This study uses a regionally refined global cloud-resolving model and the
36 pseudo-global warming approach to investigate the potential impact of global warming on
37 summertime convective storms of different sizes in the central-eastern United States. Results
38 show that warming has contrasting impacts on the large and long-lasting mesoscale convective
39 systems and small and short-duration isolated deep convection events when it comes to event
40 number and mean lifetime. In addition, both types of convective systems tend to occur closer to
41 the southern and eastern coasts under future warming. This study highlights the complexity of
42 how convective systems respond to global warming.

43 **1 Introduction**

44 Deep convection produces heavy precipitation, which has critical impacts on the water
45 and biogeochemical cycles (Chapman et al., 2021; Hu et al., 2020; Kanchebe Derbile & Abudu
46 Kasei, 2012; Motew et al., 2018). It can also affect large-scale environments and radiation
47 balance through the vertical redistribution of heat, mass, and momentum within the atmosphere
48 (Feng et al., 2011; Houze, 2004). Furthermore, deep convection is associated with many natural
49 hazards, such as tornadoes, hail, lightning, flooding, and damaging gusts, severely threatening
50 human security and property (Folger, 2013; Koehler, 2020; Taszarek et al., 2020).

51 Deep convection is generally projected to increase in frequency and intensity in a warmer
52 atmosphere due to enhanced atmospheric moisture and larger convective available potential
53 energy (CAPE) (Diffenbaugh et al., 2013; Prein et al., 2017; Trapp et al., 2007; Westra et al.,
54 2014). However, warming also often leads to increased convective inhibition (CIN) and
55 decreased inland relative humidity (RH) (Byrne & O’Gorman, 2016; Chen et al., 2020), which
56 are believed to suppress summertime deep convection in some areas of the United States
57 (Grabowski & Prein, 2019; Hoogewind et al., 2017; Taszarek et al., 2021; Trapp et al., 2019).
58 The competition between these two groups of factors (increased moisture and CAPE versus
59 greater CIN and lower RH) complicates how convective systems respond to global warming.
60 CIN and CAPE affect deep convection in different ways. CIN quantifies the negative buoyancy
61 that must be overcome to initiate convection, while CAPE measures atmospheric instability and
62 potential convective intensity but takes effect only after CIN is overcome for convective
63 initiation (Diffenbaugh et al., 2013; Trapp et al., 2007). Rasmussen et al. (2020) demonstrated

64 that, under global warming, increased CIN would suppress weak and moderate convection, while
65 larger CAPE would result in more strong convection. However, they used grid-scale radar
66 reflectivity to estimate the changes in the convection populations of different scales, which might
67 not represent the actual sizes and intensities of deep convective systems. Small and short-
68 duration isolated deep convection (IDC) can produce radar reflectivity as large as that of large
69 and long-lasting mesoscale convective systems (MCSs) (Li et al., 2021b).

70 This study exploits the updated FLExible object TRAcKeR (FLEXTRKR) algorithm to
71 distinguish small and short-duration IDC from large and long-lasting MCS events, enabling us to
72 investigate the potential impacts of future warming on these two types of convective systems
73 with distinct properties (Li et al., 2021a). Using a regionally refined global convection-
74 permitting model – the Simple Cloud-Resolving E3SM (Energy Exascale Earth System Model)
75 Atmosphere Model (SCREAM) (Caldwell et al., 2021), we simulate convective systems of
76 different sizes over the United States east of the Rocky Mountains, as they were observed in the
77 summer of 2020 and under future warming conditions. We apply the pseudo-global warming
78 (PGW) experiment framework to construct the future warming scenario for SCREAM (Schär et
79 al., 1996). The SCREAM model and configuration employed, the updated FLEXTRKR
80 algorithm, and an observational MCS-IDC dataset are described in detail in Section 2. Section 3
81 evaluates SCREAM’s performance in reproducing observed MCS and IDC characteristics and
82 analyzes the potential impacts of global warming on MCS and IDC by comparing the simulated
83 MCS and IDC events under observed and pseudo-warming conditions. The uncertainties and
84 limitations of the study are also discussed in Section 3. Finally, we summarize this study in
85 Section 4.

86 **2 Materials and Methods**

87 **2.1 SCREAM and Regional Refined Mesh**

88 SCREAM is a global convection-permitting atmospheric-land model developed by the
89 U.S. Department of Energy (DOE) designed to utilize DOE’s high-performance supercomputer
90 resources to resolve some of the long-standing problems attributed to coarse-resolution in E3SM
91 simulations (Caldwell et al., 2021). SCREAM uses the non-hydrostatic version of the High Order
92 Method Modeling Environment (HOMME-NH) as the fluid-dynamic solver (Taylor et al., 2020).
93 The model’s physical parameterizations include the Simplified Higher Order Closure (SHOC)
94 boundary layer turbulence scheme (Bogenschutz & Krueger, 2013), the Predicted Particle
95 Properties (P3) microphysics scheme (Morrison & Milbrandt, 2015), and the combination of the
96 Radiative Transfer for Energetics (RTE) and the Rapid Radiative Transfer Model for General
97 circulation models – Parallel (RRTMGP) for longwave and shortwave radiation (Pincus et al.,
98 2019). The model does not include a deep convective parameterization, and aerosol
99 concentrations are prescribed (Caldwell et al., 2021).

100 Although SCREAM is demonstrably superior to coarse-resolution E3SM in simulating
101 precipitation and convective systems, it is computationally expensive (Caldwell et al., 2021).
102 This study, thus, constructs a regional refined mesh to not only reduce the computational burden
103 but also exploit the advanced features of SCREAM (Liu et al., 2023; Tang et al., 2019).
104 Regionally refined model (RRM) supports higher resolution in the region of interest and lower
105 resolution in other areas of the model domain (Figure 1). Since the coarse resolution region does
106 not explicitly resolve deep convection, the lack of a deep convective parameterization in

107 SCREAM is a potential issue, particularly for long-running simulations. Consequently, we apply
108 nudging over the coarse-resolution region to constrain the atmospheric states by those of a global
109 reanalysis but keep the high-resolution region of interest free-running and able to respond to
110 external forcing (Figure 1). We expect nudging to generate realistic boundary conditions for the
111 region of interest, mimicking convection-permitting regional climate model simulations
112 constrained by boundary conditions (Li et al., 2023). However, nudging allows some large-scale
113 circulation feedback between the region of interest and the surrounding areas in SCREAM RRM,
114 which is entirely absent in regional climate models because of the imposed boundary conditions.

115 Using the regional refined mesh configuration in Figure 1, which has a dynamical
116 horizontal resolution of ~ 3.2 km for the central-eastern United States and ~ 25 km for other areas,
117 we conduct an AMIP-type (AMIP: Atmospheric Model Intercomparison Project) SCREAM
118 RRM control simulation (hereafter named the CTRL simulation) from June 28 to August 19,
119 2020, with the first three days as spin-up. Its component set comprises an active atmospheric
120 component, i.e., SCREAM, an active land component – E3SM Land Model (ELM) (Golaz et al.,
121 2019; Golaz et al., 2022), a simplified active sea ice component, a data ocean model with
122 prescribed hourly sea surface temperature (SST) and sea ice fractions from the European Centre
123 for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF) Reanalysis v5 (ERA5) reanalysis dataset, and
124 the Model for Scale Adaptive River Transport (MOSART) for river routing (Li et al., 2013).
125 SCREAM has 128 vertical levels with a vertical resolution of ~ 50 m in the boundary layer and a
126 model top at 2.25 hPa (Caldwell et al., 2021). The model has a dynamics time step of 8.33
127 seconds and a physics time step of 100 seconds. The atmospheric initial condition is based on a
128 combination of the hourly High-Resolution Rapid Refresh (HRRR) and ERA5 reanalysis
129 datasets (Dowell et al., 2022; Hersbach et al., 2020). HRRR has a horizontal resolution of 3 km,
130 covering the contiguous United States, while ERA5 has a global horizontal resolution of 0.25° .
131 We use HRRR wherever it is available and ERA5 for areas not covered by HRRR when
132 constructing the SCREAM atmospheric initial condition. The land initial condition is spun up
133 through a 3-year (June 28, 2017, to June 28, 2020) SCREAM RRM land-only simulation
134 constrained by atmospheric forcing in 2020 from ERA5 (Liu et al., 2023). The simulation uses
135 prescribed hourly SST from ERA5. Three-dimensional zonal (\mathbf{U}) and meridional (\mathbf{V}) winds,
136 temperature (T), and specific humidity (Q) above 850 hPa are nudged towards hourly ERA5
137 reanalysis with a relaxation timescale of 6 hours for grids outside the red box in Figure 1
138 (Barthel Sorensen et al., 2024).

139

140

141 **Figure 1.** The SCREAM RRM domain in a cylindrical equidistant projection. Blue lines
 142 represent the boundaries of spectral element grids, and each spectral element comprises 4
 143 physical grid boxes. The red rectangle outlines the free-running region within, while the green
 144 rectangle outlines the region with observational MCS-IDC data.

145

2.2 PGW setup

146 To investigate the potential impacts of global warming on MCSs and IDC, we conduct
 147 another simulation using the PGW approach (Schär et al., 1996; Xue et al., 2023) (hereafter
 148 named the PGW simulation), which is nearly identical to the CTRL simulation but with four
 149 exceptions. For the PGW simulation, 1) monthly PGW deltas (Equation 1) are added to the state
 150 variables in the atmospheric initial condition (\mathbf{U} , \mathbf{V} , T , Q , surface pressure, and skin temperature)
 151 and the ERA5 nudging fields (\mathbf{U} , \mathbf{V} , T , and Q); 2) monthly PGW deltas are added to the
 152 atmospheric forcing state variables (10-meter \mathbf{U} and \mathbf{V} , 2-meter T , 2-meter Q , and surface
 153 pressure) and monthly PGW ratios (Equation 2) are multiplied with the flux variables from the
 154 atmospheric forcing (precipitation and surface downwelling longwave and shortwave fluxes)
 155 (Lawrence et al., 2018) as forcing for the land-only simulation to provide initial conditions for
 156 the land component; 3) temporally-interpolated hourly PGW deltas are added to prescribed SST;
 157 4) the Sixth Assessment Report of the United Nations Intergovernmental Panel on Climate
 158 Change (IPCC AR6) projected greenhouse gas concentrations in 2100 are used instead of the
 159 values in 2020 (Meinshausen et al., 2019). Similar to Li et al. (2023), we select 11 models from
 160 the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project Phase 6 (CMIP6) archive (except for E3SM v1.1) to
 161 compute the multi-model mean PGW deltas and ratios between the historical period (1981–2010)
 162 and the end of this century (2071–2100) under the Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSP5-8.5)
 163 scenario, featuring a radiative forcing of 8.5 W m^{-2} by 2100. Figure S1 summarizes the
 164 workflow of the PGW simulation.

165

$$\Delta_{PGW} = X_{2071-2100} - X_{1981-2010} \quad (1)$$

$$R_{PGW} = \frac{X_{2071-2100}}{X_{1981-2010}} \quad (2)$$

167 where X is any meteorological variable (e.g., U , V , T , and Q); $X_{2071-2100}$ denotes the multi-year
 168 averaged monthly value of X between 2071 and 2100, similar to $X_{1981-2010}$; Δ_{PGW} refers to the
 169 PGW delta of X , and R_{PGW} represents the PGW ratio of X for the given month.

170 2.3 The updated FLEXTRKR algorithm and the observational MCS-IDC dataset

171 The updated FLEXTRKR algorithm, combined with the Storm Labeling in Three
 172 Dimensions (SL3D) algorithm (Starzec et al., 2017), can track MCS and IDC simultaneously
 173 using infrared brightness temperature (T_b), radar reflectivity, precipitation, and melting level
 174 height (Li et al., 2021a). The algorithm first identifies cold cloud shields (CCSs) with $T_b < 241K$
 175 at each time slice and then establishes the spatial connections of CCSs between two consecutive
 176 hours using a spatial overlap threshold of 50%. A track is generated by linking all the CCSs from
 177 the same cloud system. FLEXTRKR classifies a track as an MCS if the areas of the tracked
 178 CCSs are $>60,000 \text{ km}^2$ for >6 consecutive hours and the track contains precipitation features
 179 (PFs) with a major axis length $>100 \text{ km}$ and an embedded intense convective cell area $\geq 16 \text{ km}^2$
 180 for ≥ 6 continuous hours. Here, a PF is a continuous updraft, convective, or precipitating
 181 stratiform area with precipitation $>1 \text{ mm h}^{-1}$, and an intense convective cell is a continuous
 182 updraft or convective area with composite reflectivity $\geq 45 \text{ dBZ}$. The SL3D algorithm identifies
 183 updraft, convective, and precipitating stratiform pixels. A non-MCS track is considered IDC if it
 184 contains any PFs and convective core features (CCFs) during its lifetime. A CCF is a continuous
 185 updraft or convective area with precipitation $>0 \text{ mm h}^{-1}$.

186 This study uses the updated FLEXTRKR algorithm and various source datasets to
 187 develop a high-resolution (4 km, hourly) observational MCS-IDC dataset, which provides
 188 tracking and characteristics of MCS and IDC events over the United States east of the Rocky
 189 Mountains from July 1 to August 19, 2020. The source datasets are the same as those used in Li
 190 et al. (2021a), except that the 3-D Gridded NEXRAD (Next Generation Weather Radar) WSR-
 191 88D Radar (GridRad) reflectivity data has been updated from Version 3.1 to Version 4.2
 192 (Bowman & Homeyer, 2021). The updated FLEXTRKR is also used to track MCS and IDC
 193 events from the above SCREAM RRM simulations within the observational MCS-IDC data
 194 domain (Figure 1). Notably, we remove convective systems associated with two hurricanes
 195 (Hurricanes Hanna and Isaias) occurring during the study period from the SCREAM simulations
 196 and the observational MCS-IDC dataset. Moreover, this study focuses exclusively on MCS and
 197 IDC events in the U.S. land areas within the MCS-IDC data domain, which are defined as
 198 convective systems staying within the region for at least half of their lifetimes.

199 3 Results

200 3.1 Evaluation of the CTRL simulation

201 Table 1 evaluates the CTRL simulation against the observational MCS-IDC dataset at the
 202 event scale. The CTRL simulation roughly produces as many MCS (66 vs. 80) and IDC (19,638
 203 vs. 15,887) events as observations, far better than the underestimated counts (by $>70\%$) of MCS
 204 events in global climate models generated with refined horizontal resolution at 50 and 25 km
 205 over North America (Feng et al., 2021). The CTRL simulation also well reproduces the observed
 206 MCS and IDC respective mean lifetime, CCS area, CCS core ($T_b < 225 \text{ K}$) area, PF stratiform
 207 area, PF convective and stratiform precipitation rates, and CCS, PF, and CCF major axis lengths.

208 However, the CTRL underestimates the MCS max 40-dBZ echo top height but overestimates the
209 MCS and IDC PF convective areas. The latter may be attributed to overestimated model radar
210 reflectivities associated with convective systems (not shown), a limitation also identified in the
211 simulation of the June 2012 North American derecho using SCREAM RRM and the Weather
212 Research and Forecasting Model (Li et al., 2023; Liu et al., 2023). The CTRL also effectively
213 captures the observed MCS evolutionary characteristics (Figure S2), further validating the
214 excellent capability of SCREAM RRM in simulating the populations of convective systems.

215 Figures S3a-S3d and 2a-2d compare the CTRL-simulated spatial distributions of MCS
216 and IDC occurrences and their accumulated precipitation with the MCS-IDC dataset. The CTRL
217 captures the observed MCS and IDC spatial distribution patterns well. The uncentered pattern
218 correlations between CTRL and observations are 0.68 and 0.72 for MCS and IDC precipitation,
219 respectively (Figures 2a-2d). These values reach up to 0.93 and 0.90 for the MCS and IDC
220 occurrence frequencies (Figures S3a-S3d). The CTRL correctly identifies hotspots with frequent
221 MCS and IDC occurrences, such as the Great Plains and Midwest for MCS and the southeastern
222 and eastern coastal areas for IDC. However, on average, the CTRL underestimates the MCS
223 numbers by 23% and precipitation by 16%. The underestimation is most apparent in the Great
224 Plains, with frequent MCS occurrences, which is a common bias widely found in regional and
225 global climate models (Feng et al., 2021; Li et al., 2022; Lin et al., 2022; Prein et al., 2020). In
226 addition, on average, the CTRL overestimates IDC occurrences by 23%, while the IDC
227 precipitation is overestimated by only 5% due to an underestimated IDC precipitation rate (Table
228 1).

229 Overall, despite the presence of certain common model biases, the CTRL simulation
230 effectively captures the event-scale and spatial-scale characteristics of observed MCS and IDC
231 events. This allows for a meaningful comparison between the PGW and CTRL simulations.

232 **Table 1.** Comparison of the SCREAM RRM simulated MCS and IDC statistics and mean properties with the observational MCS-IDC dataset

Statistics and mean properties	MCS			IDC		
	Obs	CTRL	PGW	Obs	CTRL	PGW
Event number	80	66	85	15,887	19,638	16,014
Lifetime / h	18.6	18.4 ¹	17.1	1.8	1.5	1.6
CCS area / km ²	127,560	116,552	113,209	2,970	2,927	3,546
CCS major axis length / km	524	515	508	67	75	77
CCS core area / km ²	66,444	55,516	61,202	667	647	1,103
PF major axis length / km	297	323	317	47	59	57
PF convective area / km ²	8,363	12,911	15,027	388	970	1,020
PF stratiform area / km ²	22,405	27,325	25,159	558	777	651
PF convective precipitation rate / mm h ⁻¹	4.6	4.1	3.9	4.3	3.7	3.7
PF stratiform precipitation rate / mm h ⁻¹	2.8	2.6	2.6	2.9	2.2	2.3
Max 40-dBZ echo top height / km	9.2	6.9	8.1	5.4	5.0	6.2
CCF major axis length / km	122	114	129	26	42	44

233 ¹Red colored numbers indicate the difference between the PGW and CTRL simulations is statistically significant at the 5% level.

234

235

236 **Figure 2.** Spatial distributions of accumulated precipitation produced by (**left panel**) MCS and
 237 (**right panel**) IDC events from (**a, b**) the observational MCS-IDC dataset, (**c, d**) the CTRL
 238 simulation, and (**e, f**) the PGW simulation. We only count hours with hourly precipitation larger
 239 than 0.01 mm for each grid cell.

240 3.2 Impact of global warming on event-scale statistics

241 By comparing the PGW and CTRL simulations, we find consistent increases in the mean
 242 PF convective areas of MCS and IDC events, which aligns with larger max 40-dBZ echo top
 243 heights under warming (Figure 3 and Table 1). In contrast, MCS and IDC PF stratiform areas are
 244 reduced in the PGW compared to the CTRL simulations (Figure 3 and Table 1). The warming-
 245 induced increase in MCS convective areas and decrease in stratiform areas is consistent with
 246 Feng et al. (2024), who investigated the potential impact of global warming on a cluster of
 247 springtime MCSs in the southern Great Plains during May 2015. They attributed the wider
 248 convective areas to larger CAPE, resulting in more intense convective updrafts, and the reduced
 249 stratiform areas to elevated stratiform cloud bases, leading to stronger precipitation evaporation
 250 in a warmer atmosphere (Feng et al., 2024). Additionally, Figure 3 and Table 1 show a stronger

251 warming impact on the MCS convective area than the IDC, implying that large convective
 252 systems may be more sensitive to warming-induced factors (enhanced CAPE and moisture)
 253 favorable for convective development than small convective systems. This can be further
 254 confirmed by an increase of 29% in the number of MCSs but an unexpected decrease of 18% in
 255 the IDC number (Figure 3 and Table 1). More surprisingly, the MCS mean lifetime decreases by
 256 7.4%, while the IDC mean lifetime increases by 9.4%.

257

258 **Figure 3.** Relative changes in the occurrence number, mean lifetime, and PF convective and
 259 stratiform areas of MCS and IDC events from the PGW compared to the CTRL simulation.
 260 Notably, all the differences are statistically significant at the 5% level, except for the MCS PF
 261 stratiform area and the MCS and IDC event numbers. The former does not pass the Student's t-
 262 test at the 5% level. Additionally, we lack sufficient samples to determine the significance of the
 263 changes in MCS and IDC event numbers, which necessitate ensemble or multiple seasons of
 264 simulations.

265 Figure 4 compares the environmental conditions between the PGW and CTRL
 266 simulations. As expected, warming leads to higher surface temperature, more moisture, and
 267 generally larger CAPE and CIN (Figures 4a and 4c-3e). As mentioned in Section 1, enhanced
 268 CAPE and moisture favor convective development, while larger CIN may suppress convection

269 initiation. We propose several hypotheses below to explain the aforementioned contrasting MCS
270 and IDC responses to global warming.

271 First, we hypothesize weak and small convective systems have the energy or lifting
272 mechanism to overcome a small CIN but cannot overcome a large CIN. The warming-induced
273 increase in CIN may suppress convective initiation of these potentially weak convective systems.
274 This hypothesis is similar to that proposed by Rasmussen et al. (2020) and can explain the
275 reduction in the absolute IDC number in the PGW simulation (Figure 3). Besides, the probability
276 density function of the IDC lifetimes shows that the suppression effect is the most significant for
277 IDC events with a lifetime of 1 hour (Figure S4b), the fraction of which is reduced by 3.7%.
278 Notably, 1 hour is the minimum lifetime an IDC event can have as defined in this study. In
279 contrast, the fractions of IDC events with longer lifetimes generally increase, leading to an
280 overall longer IDC mean lifetime (Figure 3).

281 Second, potentially strong and large convective systems can overcome a large CIN, and
282 their initiations are insensitive to warming-induced enhancement in CIN; however, their
283 development is sensitive to CAPE. A larger CAPE in a warmer atmosphere intensifies these
284 strong convective systems. This hypothesis can also partially explain the increased fraction of
285 IDC events with longer lifetimes in Figure S4b. If this were the case, some IDC events might
286 even grow into MCSs, leading to an increase in the number of MCS events under warming
287 (Figure 3). However, these new MCSs found only in the PGW should lie in the lower tail of the
288 MCS lifetime probability density function (Figure S4a). This increases the fraction of MCSs with
289 relatively shorter lifetimes, reducing the MCS mean lifetime (Figure 3).

290 Third, due to their intensification under global warming, some IDC events may merge to
291 form a large convective system or even an MCS, leading to an increase in the fraction of IDC
292 events with longer lifetimes or MCSs with relatively shorter lifetimes (Figure S4).

293 A theoretical study is being conducted to further validate the above hypotheses at the
294 event scale. The distinct response of MCS and IDC to global warming is reminiscent of the “wet
295 gets wetter and dry gets drier” paradigm (Held & Soden, 2006): strong gets stronger and weak
296 gets weaker (or disappears entirely) for convective systems.

297

298 **Figure 4.** Differences in mean environmental conditions between the PGW and CTRL
 299 simulations. (a) 2-meter temperature. (b) Sea level pressure. (c) Precipitable water. (d) CAPE.
 300 (e) CIN. (f) cloud fraction. (g) RH at 850 hPa. (h) Geopotential height (colored shading) and
 301 wind field (vectors) at 850 hPa. (i) Geopotential height (colored shading) and wind field
 302 (vectors) at 200 hPa. We exclude all MCS- and IDC-covered grid cells when compositing the
 303 environmental conditions.

304 3.3 Impact of global warming on spatial characteristics

305 Besides influencing MCS and IDC event-scale statistics, warming also changes the
 306 spatial distributions of MCS and IDC occurrences and associated precipitation (Figures S3 and
 307 2). The region with the most frequent MCS occurrences (and associated precipitation) shifts from
 308 the northern Great Plains in the CTRL simulation to the Midwest and the lower Mississippi
 309 Valley in the PGW simulation. IDC's inland hotspot in the Midwest diminishes under warming;
 310 instead, IDC preferentially occurs in the U.S. eastern and southeastern coastal areas in a warmer
 311 atmosphere. The tendency of MCS and IDC to occur closer to the southern and eastern coastal
 312 areas is attributed to the alteration of the large-scale circulation due to global warming (Figure
 313 4). Namely, the spatially uneven (more in the north and less in the south) increases in surface
 314 temperature under global warming result in lower sea level pressure in the eastern United States
 315 but higher sea level pressure in nearby marine and mountainous areas (Figures 4a-4b). Such a
 316 pressure anomaly pattern leads to low-level convergence in the southern and eastern coastal
 317 areas and high-level divergence in the eastern coastal areas (Figures 4h-4i), facilitating
 318 convective initiation and development in these two regions. Moreover, the low-level
 319 convergence increases the low-level RH in the coastal areas, while the low-level RH is

320 remarkably reduced in the inland northern Great Plains. The near-surface RH is critical in
 321 regulating convective systems (Li et al., 2023; Taszarek et al., 2021). The increase in RH also
 322 favors the development of MCS and IDC events in the southern and eastern coastal areas, as
 323 corroborated by the larger cloud fractions in coastal areas in the PGW than in the CTRL
 324 simulations. Wind shear is another factor that may contribute to the shift in regions with frequent
 325 MCS and IDC occurrences. Under warming conditions, low-level (0-3 km) and mid-level (0-6
 326 km) wind shears are enhanced in the eastern and southern coastal areas but suppressed in the
 327 inland Great Plains and Midwest regions (Figure 5). Increased wind shear magnitudes may
 328 facilitate the initiation and development of convective systems by enhancing the updraft-relative
 329 inflow, which widens updrafts and reduces their susceptibility to entrainment-driven dilution
 330 (Peters et al., 2022).

331
 332 **Figure 5.** Same as Figure 4 but for environmental wind shears (**a:** 0-3 km; **b:** 0-6 km).

333 3.4 Uncertainties

334 A notable limitation of the study is the short simulation length of only 50 days. This has a
 335 minor impact on IDC due to the large number of IDC events, with all differences in IDC
 336 properties between the PGW and CTRL simulations being statistically significant (Table 1).
 337 However, fewer than 100 MCS events are identified during the period, and the differences in
 338 most MCS properties do not pass the Student's t-test at the 5% level (Table 1). Longer or
 339 ensemble simulations are necessary to draw more robust conclusions.

340 Although our PGW and CTRL simulations are short, some of their differences align with
 341 the PGW deltas derived from CMIP6 models (Figures 4 and 6). These include the amplified
 342 warming from the tropics toward the poles, the more considerable increase in water vapor
 343 content in the eastern and southern coasts compared to inland areas, and the low-level
 344 convergence anomaly in the Southeast. These similarities validate our PGW approach and
 345 support our conclusion about the shift in MCS and IDC locations. Nevertheless, the PGW deltas

346 of wind fields at 850 hPa and 200 hPa differ from those computed by the PGW and CTRL
 347 simulations. This discrepancy is expected, as the PGW and CTRL simulations consider the
 348 immediate impact of simulated weather systems on large-scale circulations, while PGW deltas
 349 are based on multi-year and multi-model ensemble means, which substantially reduce model
 350 uncertainties and interannual variability.

351
 352 **Figure 6.** Spatial distributions of averaged PGW deltas of (a) temperature at 1000 hPa, (b)
 353 specific humidity and wind field at 850 hPa, and (c) specific humidity and wind field at 200 hPa
 354 during July and August.

355 4 Conclusions

356 We investigate how summertime convective systems of different sizes (MCS vs. IDC)
 357 could unfold in the central-eastern U.S. by the end of this century, under SSP5-8.5, as simulated
 358 in SCREAM with regional refinement and the pseudo-global warming method. An updated
 359 FLEXTRKR algorithm is used to identify MCS and IDC events from the SCREAM RRM
 360 simulations. The SCREAM RRM can faithfully reproduce the observed MCS and IDC
 361 characteristics between July 1 and August 19, 2020, at both event and spatial scales. By
 362 comparing MCS and IDC events under the present climate (the CTRL simulation) with those
 363 under global warming (the PGW simulation), we find that warming leads to more MCS but
 364 fewer IDC occurrences, although the convective areas of both MCS and IDC events are expected
 365 to increase due to larger CAPE. However, the MCS mean lifetime is reduced, while the IDC
 366 mean lifetime increases under warming. The contrasting responses of MCS and IDC to global
 367 warming may be related to the different roles of enhanced CAPE and CIN in the initiation and
 368 development of convective systems of different intensities. Larger CIN would suppress the
 369 initiation of weak and small IDC events, resulting in fewer IDC occurrences but a relatively
 370 longer mean lifetime. Larger CAPE would intensify strong IDC events, which may grow upscale
 371 to be considered MCSs. However, these new MCSs are expected to be smaller and have shorter
 372 lifetimes than those events that already exist as MCSs under present-day conditions. Therefore,
 373 although warming increases the MCS number, their mean lifetime is reduced. Additionally, we
 374 find that both MCS and IDC events tend to occur closer to the U.S. southern and eastern coastal

375 areas under warming. Global warming produces a low-level convergence anomaly and larger RH
376 and wind shears in these areas, facilitating the initiation and development of convective systems.
377 As the first study to investigate the impact of global warming on convective systems at different
378 scales, this work unveils the complexity of the responses of convective systems to climate
379 change and motivates further research to understand the underlying mechanisms for various
380 changes of MCS and IDC using cloud-resolving and theoretical models.

381

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400

401 **Open Research**

402 The SCREAM source code is available at <https://github.com/E3SM-Project/scream> (last access: September 26,
403 2022). The MCS-IDC dataset used in the study is available at
404 https://portal.nersc.gov/project/m3780/jli628/SCREAM_MCS_IDC/ (last access: January 26, 2023). The
405 GridRad v4.2 data is from <https://rda.ucar.edu/datasets/ds841-1/> (last access: November 3, 2022) (Bowman &
406 Homeyer, 2021). We download the ERA5 nudging fields and SST from <https://rda.ucar.edu/datasets/ds633-0/>
407 (last access: October 2, 2022) (ECMWF, 2019). The HRRR reanalysis data is downloaded from the Google
408 Cloud Platform ([https://console.cloud.google.com/marketplace/product/noaa-public/hrrr?project=python-
409 232920&pli=1](https://console.cloud.google.com/marketplace/product/noaa-public/hrrr?project=python-232920&pli=1); last access, December 7, 2022). Surface variables in the ERA5 initial condition and the ERA5
410 forcing data used in the SCREAM land-only simulations are downloaded from
411 <https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/cdsapp#!/dataset/reanalysis-era5-single-levels?tab=overview> (last access:
412 December 26, 2022) (Hersbach et al., 2023b). Pressure-level variables in the ERA5 initial condition are
413 downloaded from [https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/cdsapp#!/dataset/reanalysis-era5-pressure-
414 levels?tab=overview](https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/cdsapp#!/dataset/reanalysis-era5-pressure-levels?tab=overview) (last access: December 26, 2022) (Hersbach et al., 2023a). We download the CMIP6 data
415 from <https://aims2.llnl.gov/search/cmip6/> (last access: December 26, 2022) (Boucher et al., 2019; Boucher et
416 al., 2018; Danabasoglu, 2019a, 2019b; Dix et al., 2019a, 2019b; EC-Earth, 2019a, 2019b; Guo et al., 2018a;
417 Guo et al., 2018b; Jungclaus et al., 2019; Lovato & Peano, 2020a, 2020b; Seland et al., 2019a, 2019b;
418 Shiogama et al., 2019; Swart et al., 2019a, 2019b; Tatebe & Watanabe, 2018; Wieners et al., 2019; Yu, 2019a,
419 2019b).

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422 **References**

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